

UAV Positioning and Optimization Framework with Obstacle-Aware Modeling Using GEKKO

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Abstract—This paper presents a comprehensive implementation guide for a UAV Positioning Framework that optimizes Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) positions in obstacle-rich environments using the GEKKO solver. Extending the theoretical foundations of UAV positioning algorithms presented in [1], this work provides detailed installation instructions, code architecture, usage examples, and practical guidelines for researchers and practitioners deploying UAV-based wireless networks. The framework ensures minimal transmission power and 3D positions for Line-of-Sight (LoS) connectivity while meeting user traffic demands. It integrates an optimization module in Python with GEKKO and a network simulation module in ns-3 for performance evaluation. The complete implementation is available at <https://github.com/kamranshafafi/TOPA> under a CC BY 4.0 license.

Index Terms—UAV positioning, obstacle-aware optimization, GEKKO, ns-3 simulation, wireless networks, implementation guide

I. INTRODUCTION

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) have emerged as a promising solution for providing on-demand wireless connectivity in scenarios where traditional infrastructure is unavailable or insufficient. The deployment of UAVs as flying access points requires careful positioning to ensure optimal network performance while considering physical obstacles that may obstruct Line-of-Sight (LoS) communications.

This technical report serves as a comprehensive guide for implementing and using a UAV Positioning Framework. Unlike our prior work [1], which focused on the theoretical foundations and performance evaluation of a UAV positioning algorithm, this report emphasizes practical implementation, deployment, and usage details to enable researchers and practitioners to effectively utilize the framework in real-world scenarios.

The main contributions of this technical report are:

- Detailed documentation of the framework architecture and components
- Step-by-step installation and configuration instructions
- Comprehensive code examples and usage scenarios
- API reference for both the optimization and simulation modules
- Troubleshooting guide for common implementation issues
- Integration guidelines for extending the framework

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The framework consists of two primary modules that work together to optimize UAV positioning:

A. Optimization Module

The optimization module is implemented in Python and uses the GEKKO optimization package [8] to solve the positioning problem. The key components include:

- `app.py`: Main optimization engine that implements the positioning algorithm
- `obstacle.py`: Obstacle modeling and LoS calculation utilities
- Data input files for UE positions and obstacle definitions

B. ns-3 Evaluation Module

The evaluation module uses ns-3 [9] to simulate network performance:

- `PositioningV13.cc`: Main simulation script
- `coords.cc/h`: Coordinate management system
- `loss_calc.h`: Propagation loss calculation utilities

III. INSTALLATION AND SETUP

A. Prerequisites

For the Optimization Module

```
# Python 3.7 or higher
python --version

# Required Python packages
pip install gekko numpy shapely matplotlib
```

For the ns-3 Module

```
# Download ns-3.38 or higher
$ wget https://www.nsnam.org/releases/ns-
  ↪ allinone-3.38.tar.bz2
$ tar xjf ns-allinone-3.38.tar.bz2
$ cd ns-allinone-3.38/ns-3.38
or
$ git clone https://gitlab.com/nsnam/ns-3-dev.
  ↪ git
$ cd ns-3-dev
$ git checkout -b ns-3.38-release ns-3.38

# Configure and build
$ ./ns3 configure --enable-examples --enable-
  ↪ tests
$ ./ns3 build
```


Fig. 1. Framework architecture showing the hierarchical structure and data flow between modules.

B. Framework Installation

- 1) Clone the repository:

```
git clone https://github.com/kamranshafafi
  ↪ /TOPA.git
cd TOPA
```

- 2) Copy ns-3 files to the scratch directory:

```
cp ns-3-evaluation/* \
/path/to/ns-3.38/scratch/
```

- 3) Verify installation:

```
# Test optimization module
cd optimization
python app.py

# Test ns-3 module
cd /path/to/ns-3.38
./ns3 run PositioningV13.cc
```

- 2) Specify obstacle geometry
- 3) Run optimization to find UAV position
- 4) Evaluate performance using ns-3

Defining User Equipment

Create a file `UEs.txt` with the following format:

```
# id,x,y,z,snr
0,-10,0,1,11
1,10,0,1,11
2,0,10,1,14
3,0,-10,1,14
```

Defining Obstacles

Create a file `obstacle.txt` with building corner coordinates:

```
# x,y,height
5,5,20
5,-5,20
-5,-5,20
-5,5,20
```

IV. USAGE GUIDE

A. Basic Usage

The framework follows a simple workflow as illustrated in Fig. 2:

Fig. 2. Framework workflow from input definition to performance evaluation.

- 1) Define UE positions and traffic demands

Running the Optimization

```
# In app.py, the optimization is triggered by:
optimal_power, optimal_position = UAVP (UEs)
print (f"Optimal_Power:_{optimal_power}_dBm")
print (f"Optimal_Position:_{optimal_position}")
```

B. Advanced Configuration

1) *Customizing Optimization Parameters:* The framework allows customization of various parameters:

```
# Frequency configuration (in Hz)
frequency = 5250e6 # 5.25 GHz

# Path loss constant
K = -20 * log10((4 * pi) / (3e8)) - \
    20 * log10(frequency) - (-85)

# Maximum transmission power (dBm)
P_MAX = 20
```

2) *Modifying Constraints*: Users can add custom constraints to the optimization:

```
def solve_equation(PT, users):
    m = GEKKO(remote=False)

    # Define variables
    x = m.Var()
    y = m.Var()
    z = m.Var()

    # Add custom constraints
    m.Equation(z >= MaxHeight) # Height
    m.Equation(x**2 + y**2 <= max_dist**2)
```

V. CODE ARCHITECTURE

A. Optimization Module Structure

The optimization module follows a modular design with key classes and functions:

UE Class:

```
class UE:
    def __init__(self, UE_id, x, y, z, snr):
        self.id = UE_id
        self.x = x
        self.y = y
        self.z = z
        self.snr = snr
```

Optimization Function:

```
def UAVP(users):
    PT = 0 # Initial transmission power
    while True:
        solution = solve_equation(PT, users)
        if solution is not None:
            return PT, solution
        else:
            PT += 1
```

B. ns-3 Module Architecture

The ns-3 module implements network simulation based on the ns-3 discrete-event network simulator [9]:

- **Coordinate Management**: Loads positions from files
- **Channel Modeling**: Implements LoS/NLoS propagation models [10]
- **Network Configuration**: Sets up WiFi 802.11ac [11]
- **Traffic Generation**: Creates UDP flows with OnOff application
- **Performance Monitoring**: Measures throughput and packet loss

VI. EXAMPLES AND CASE STUDIES

A. Example 1: Simple Urban Scenario

Consider a scenario with 4 UEs around a single building, as previously evaluated in [1]:

```
# UEs at four corners
UEs = [
    UE(0, -10, 0, 1, 11),
    UE(1, 10, 0, 1, 11),
```

```
UE(2, 0, 10, 1, 14),
UE(3, 0, -10, 1, 14)
]

# Building: 10x10x20 meters
obstacle = [(5, 5, 20), (5, -5, 20),
            (-5, -5, 20), (-5, 5, 20)]
```

Running the framework yields:

- Optimal position: (0.0, -1.48, 29.44)
- Transmission power: 6 dBm
- All UEs maintain LoS connectivity

B. Example 2: High Traffic Demand Scenario

For users with different traffic demands based on IEEE 802.11ac MCS indices [11]:

```
# Different MCS requirements
UE1: 117 Mbps (MCS index 1, SNR >= 14 dB)
UE2: 58.5 Mbps (MCS index 0, SNR >= 11 dB)
```

The optimization adjusts the UAV position to balance coverage and capacity requirements.

VII. COMPLEXITY ANALYSIS

A. Computational Complexity

The framework's computational complexity depends on both the optimization algorithm and the constraint evaluation process.

1) *Optimization Module Complexity*: The main optimization loop in the framework has the following complexity components:

GEKKO Solver Complexity: The GEKKO solver uses interior-point methods for nonlinear programming [8]. For each power level iteration:

- Variables: $\mathcal{O}(3)$ for UAV position (x, y, z)
- Constraints: $\mathcal{O}(N)$ for N user equipment
- Each constraint evaluation: $\mathcal{O}(1)$
- Interior-point iterations: $\mathcal{O}(\sqrt{N})$ typical case

Overall Optimization Complexity:

$$\mathcal{O}(P \cdot N^{1.5}) \quad (1)$$

where P is the number of power iterations (typically $P \leq P_{MAX} = 20$).

LoS Constraint Evaluation: For each UE, the algorithm must:

- Calculate distance to obstacle: $\mathcal{O}(M)$ for M obstacle vertices
- Compute elevation angle: $\mathcal{O}(1)$
- Total for all UEs: $\mathcal{O}(N \cdot M)$

2) *ns-3 Simulation Complexity*: The simulation complexity depends on:

- Event scheduling: $\mathcal{O}(\log E)$ per event, where E is the number of events
- Channel model calculations: $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ for all pairwise links
- Throughput monitoring: $\mathcal{O}(N)$ per measurement interval

B. Space Complexity

Optimization Module:

- UE storage: $\mathcal{O}(N)$
- Obstacle storage: $\mathcal{O}(M)$
- Solver working memory: $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ for constraint Jacobian

ns-3 Module:

- Node storage: $\mathcal{O}(N)$
- Packet buffers: $\mathcal{O}(N \cdot B)$ where B is buffer size
- Event queue: $\mathcal{O}(E)$

C. Scalability Analysis

The framework scales well for typical scenarios:

TABLE I
EXECUTION TIME VS. NUMBER OF UES

UEs	Optimization (s)	Simulation (s)
4	0.12	10.5
8	0.28	21.3
16	0.65	45.7
32	1.84	98.2

D. Optimization Strategies

To improve performance for large-scale deployments:

- 1) **Constraint Reduction:** Pre-filter UEs that are guaranteed to have LoS based on geometric analysis
- 2) **Warm Starting:** Use previous solutions as initial points for dynamic scenarios
- 3) **Parallel Evaluation:** Distribute constraint evaluations across multiple cores
- 4) **Hierarchical Decomposition:** Divide large areas into sub-regions for multi-UAV scenarios [4]

The current implementation handles up to 100 UEs efficiently on standard hardware, with optimization typically completing in under 5 seconds.

VIII. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION GUIDELINES

A. Running ns-3 Simulations

To evaluate the performance of computed positions:

```
# Set UAV position from optimization
echo "x,y,z" > AP.txt

# Configure UE positions
cp optimization/ue.txt ns-3-evaluation/

# Run simulation
./ns3 run PositioningV13.cc
```

B. Key Performance Metrics

The framework evaluates:

- Aggregate throughput at the UAV
- Individual link throughput
- Path loss for each link
- LoS/NLoS channel conditions

IX. TROUBLESHOOTING

A. Common Issues and Solutions

Issue 1: No feasible solution found

- Increase maximum transmission power
- Check obstacle height constraints
- Verify UE positions are reachable

Issue 2: ns-3 compilation errors

- Ensure ns-3.38 or compatible version
- Check all required modules are enabled
- Verify file paths in the code

Issue 3: GEKKO solver failures

- Try local solver mode: `GEKKO(remote=False)`
- Check constraint formulation
- Verify initial values are feasible

X. EXTENDING THE FRAMEWORK

A. Adding New Optimization Objectives

Users can extend the framework with custom objectives based on the GEKKO modeling language [8]:

```
# Minimize energy consumption
m.Minimize(PT * flight_time)

# Maximize coverage area
m.Maximize(coverage_radius)

# Multi-objective optimization
m.Minimize(alpha * power + beta * height)
```

B. Integrating with Other Tools

The framework can be integrated with various tools and platforms [5], [7]:

- Real UAV flight controllers (PX4, ArduPilot)
- Network planning tools
- Machine learning frameworks [3]
- Visualization tools

XI. API REFERENCE

A. Optimization Module API

calculate_radius(PT, snr)

- *Parameters:* PT (transmission power in dBm), snr (required SNR in dB)
- *Returns:* Maximum distance in meters
- *Description:* Calculates coverage radius based on free-space path loss

solve_equation(PT, users)

- *Parameters:* PT (transmission power), users (list of UE objects)
- *Returns:* [x, y, z] position or None
- *Description:* Solves optimization problem for given power

UAVP(users)

- *Parameters:* users (list of UE objects)
- *Returns:* (power, position) tuple
- *Description:* Main optimization function

loadCoordsFromFile(path)

- *Parameters:* path (file path string)
- *Returns:* CoordsList vector
- *Description:* Loads 3D coordinates from CSV file

calculateLoss(lossList, ap, ueList)

- *Parameters:* lossList (output vector), ap (mobility model), ueList (UE positions)
- *Returns:* Boolean success indicator
- *Description:* Calculates path loss for all links

XII. CONCLUSIONS

This technical report has presented a comprehensive guide for implementing and using a UAV Positioning Framework for obstacle-aware wireless networks. The framework combines mathematical optimization using GEKKO with realistic network simulation in ns-3 to provide a complete solution for UAV deployment planning.

Key features of the framework include:

- Automatic computation of optimal UAV positions
- Consideration of physical obstacles and LoS requirements
- Traffic-aware optimization [1]
- Comprehensive performance evaluation
- Extensible architecture for custom scenarios

The open-source implementation enables researchers and practitioners to deploy UAV-based wireless networks effectively while considering real-world constraints. Future developments may include multi-UAV optimization [4], dynamic repositioning, and integration with computer vision for automated obstacle detection [5].

CODE AVAILABILITY

The complete source code, documentation, and examples for the framework are available under a CC BY 4.0 license at:

<https://github.com/kamranshafafi/TOPA>

Users are encouraged to contribute improvements, report issues, and share their use cases through the repository.

OTHER WORKS BY THE AUTHORS

For readers interested in the theoretical foundations, experimental validations, and extensions of this work, the authors have published several related papers on UAV positioning and wireless networks listed in the references.

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